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Open Letter to the International H63D Syndrome Research Consortium
**Congratulations for having discovered
Oshtoran Syndrome a second time**

I trust this letter finds you in excellent health and high spirits. First, I commend those members of your consortium who have contributed to the groundbreaking work on what the Western medical community terms as “PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome.” Their efforts mark a significant leap forward in a field that has, hitherto, been comparatively neglected.

With a sense of humility, I acknowledge the challenges we faced in adhering to international scientific publishing standards when we first described Oshtoran Syndrome in 2016. The intricate political landscape of our nation, replete with a complex web of sanctions and both explicit and implicit social regulations, has unfortunately curtailed our ability to disseminate our findings appropriately. Rest assured that these limitations, which we fully recognize, are not indicative of any lapses in scientific rigor but are circumstantial, beyond our control.

We extend our heartfelt gratitude to Rahul Gupta, Hamed Zahedi, and Samantha Smith et. al. for their commendable work in 2022. Their paper, ‘Oshtoran Syndrome meets Spider-Man: How a group of Iranian amateur researchers inadvertently influenced pop culture,’ has clarified the situation with remarkable care, respect, and cultural sensitivity. While we find the term ‘amateurs’ not entirely fitting in this context, we nevertheless appreciate the effort and attention dedicated to the subject.

Initially, our research was concentrated on what we perceived to be a genetic disease affecting a specific tribe within Iran’s multi-ethnic tapestry. This approach not only facilitated our primary discovery but also risked isolating Oshtoran Syndrome within our national boundaries. This was further complicated by social stigmas associated with genetic disorders and the fraught dynamics of inter-ethnic relationships that have historically sustained our country. We understand now that the mutation in question is neither exotic nor confined to one specific Iranian tribe.

ZAFARIAN & Colleagues

For these reasons, we offer an apology to the scientific community. We also extend our thanks to the young team of researchers who have sought to elucidate our role in the discovery and definition of Oshtoran Syndrome, even if they may lack the full contextual understanding of our situation.

In an unexpected twist, our work has received attention due to its incorporation into pop culture phenomena like Marvel's Spider-Man series. While we may not be the target demographic for such American media, it is remarkable that popular culture has the ability to stimulate scientific curiosity across various cultural, national, and even oceanic boundaries.

We propose to retain "Oshtoran Syndrome" as either the primary or secondary nomenclature for the condition. We further suggest that "PANS-H63D-Multisystemic Instability Syndrome" and "Oshtoran Syndrome" be unified as a single entity, with at least two distinct subtypes. All relevant data have been forwarded to members of your consortium for further research. Our core objective remains aiding the afflicted, and we encourage the international medical community to recognize the legitimacy of this syndrome, despite existing gaps in understanding its pathomechanism.

In closing, I express my deepest gratitude for your consortium's transformative contributions to this nascent field. I look forward with great anticipation to the accomplishments that your team will undoubtedly achieve.

Yours sincerely,

Dr. Zafarian